

Interaction of Bis-Methyl/Benzyl Formamidine Disulphide Dihydrobromides with certain Ketones: Formation of Thiazoles and Thiazolines

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The reaction of bis-methyl and benzyl formamidine disulphide dihydrobromides with acetone, ethyl methyl ketone, acetophenone, ethyl acetoacetate and cyclohexanone has been investigated. Excepting the case of ethyl acetoacetate and acetone where the usual 2-alkylamino thiazoles were obtained, the isomeric 3-alkyl-4-thiazolines were the exclusive products of the reaction. Cyclohexanone afforded in addition a benzothiazine derivative.

The reaction of bis-formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide with ketones has been shown by King and Ryden¹ to afford 2-aminothiazoles derivatives, obtained earlier by the direct interaction of thiocarbamides with the corresponding α -haloketones. On extension of this reaction to aryl substituted bisformamidine disulphide dihydrobromides, formation of certain other compounds, notably, thiazine and thiouracil derivatives, was observed² in addition to the expected thiazolo derivatives. In the context of these results and the earlier findings of King and Ryden it was of interest to see how alkyl substituents affected the mode of reaction. The reaction of bis-benzyl/methyl formamidine disulphide dihydrobromides with the same ketones was therefore investigated.

Both bis-benzyl as well as bis methyl formamidine disulphide salts afforded analogous products. In contrast to the aryl derivatives (where R=phenyl and *p*-tolyl), these on reaction with acetone provided, instead of the expected 2-alkylamino-4, 6, 6-trimethyl-2, 3-dihydro 1, 3, 6-thiazines,³ 2-benzylamino-4-methyl thiazole (II) and 2-imino-3, 4-dimethyl-4-thiazoline (I), respectively. The exocyclic imino group of (I) was confirmed by positive phenyl isothiocyanate and carbon disulphide reactions³. Ethyl methyl ketone gave 2-imino-3-alkyl-4,5-dimethyl-4-thiazoline(s) (III). Analogously, acetophenone formed 2-imino-3-alkyl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline(s) (IV). Ethyl acetoacetate which afforded a mixture of thiazole and thiouracil derivatives on reaction with bis-arylformamidine-disulphide salts², was in the present case found to produce a single reaction product, the 2-alkylamino-5-carbethoxy-4-methyl thiazole(s) (VI). Cyclohexanone afforded two products: the spiro [(2-alkylimino-1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8-hexahydro-3, 1, 4-)benzothiazine-4, 1'-cyclohexane] (VII) and the 3-alkyl-2-imino-4, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydro-benzothiazoline(s) (VIII). The 2-mercaptoquinazoline²(IX) and 2-alkylaminotetrahydro benzothiazole(X), isomeric with VII and

1. King and Ryden, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1947, **69**, 1813.

2. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem.*, in the press.

3. Joshua, *Indian J. Chem.* 1963, **1**, 391.

VIII respectively, were not formed, although analogous products were isolated in considerable quantities in the case of aryl substituted bis-formamidine disulphide salt reactions.

It was interesting to observe that in all cases, of the two likely isomeric products *viz.*, thiazole and thiazoline, only one was exclusively formed. It is not improbable that the more labile isomer even if it were formed initially, got converted into the stable form. We, however, failed to confirm this within the limited range investigated (*vide* Experimental).

The structure 2-methylamino-4-methyl thiazole (IIA), assigned earlier⁴⁻⁶ to the product of reaction of α -bromoacetone with methyl thiocarbamide, on re-investigation, appeared to be 2-imino-3,4-dimethyl-4-thiazoline (I) as it was found reactive towards phenyl isothiocyanate and carbon disulphide.

With a view to confirming the structures (IV-VIII), reaction of phenacyl bromide ethyl α -chloro-acetoacetate,⁷ cyclohexyl cyclohexanone hydrochloride⁸ and 2-chloro cyclohexanone⁹, with methyl/benzyl thiocarbamides was investigated. The two products from phenacyl bromide although isomeric with IVA and IVB were found to be different and were

4. Traumann, *Annalen*, 1888, 249, 31.

5. Bartles *et al*, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1925, 588.

6. Wilson and Woodger, *ibid.* 1953, 2945.

7. Dey, *ibid.* 1915, 107, 1646.

8. Hüchel *et al*, *Annalen*, 1930, 477, 119.

9. Newman *et al*, *Org. Syn. Coll. Vol. III*, 189.

probably VA and VB as they did not respond to isothiocyanate and carbon disulphide reactions. The products from ethyl α -chloro acetoacetate and cyclohexyl cyclohexanone hydrochloride were found to be identical with VI and VII, respectively. 2-chloro cyclohexanone on reaction with methyl thiocarbamide afforded VIII; with benzyl thiocarbamide, however, X was obtained. These results have been summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

A mechanism has been already proposed⁸ for this reaction and holds good equally for the parent bis-formamidine disulphide salts as well as its alkyl and aryl derivatives. The greater complexity of the products in the case of bis-arylformamidine-disulphide salt and preferential, even exclusive, formation of 2-alkylamino thiazoles or 2-imino-3-alkyl-4-thiazolines, in absence of definite evidence of their interconversion, need to be explained and are being further investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general working procedure was as follows:

Bis-methyl/benzyl formamidine disulphide salt (1/100th mole) and the required ketone (slightly more than 1/100th mole)⁸ were heated at 110-120° for 3 to 4 hr. The reaction mixture after cooling was treated with acetone, filtered and the acetone insoluble solid crystallised from dilute hydrobromic acid. The products were the hydrobromides of thiazoles/thiazolines (*vide* Table 1). The free bases from most of the products could not be obtained pure; their reactions were, therefore, studied in alcoholic solutions.

The reaction mixture in the case of ethyl acetoacetate was basified with dilute sodium hydroxide and the free base, 2-alkylamino-4-methyl-5-carbomethoxy thiazole, directly filtered out. The product from cyclohexanone on similar basification yielded a semisolid which was crystallised from methanol and identified as spiro [(2-alkylimino 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8-hexahydro-3, 1, 4-benzothiazine-4, 1'-cyclohexane) (VII) by its synthesis from cyclohexyl cyclohexanone hydrochloride⁸ and methyl/benzyl thiocarbamide (*vide* Table 2). The methanol soluble portion from the above reaction, on evaporation of the solvent and crystallisation of the residue from dilute hydrochloric acid afforded a hydrochloride identified as 2-imino-3-methyl/benzyl-4, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydro-benzothiazolino (VIII). These experiments have been summarised in Table 1.

2-Imino-3,4-dimethyl-4-thiazoline hydrobromide (IA). A mixture of bis-methyl formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide (3.5 g), acetone (100 ml) and water (10 ml) were refluxed for 16 hr. and filtered. The residue (0.6 g) was found to be unchanged bis-methyl formamidine disulphide. On concentration of the filtrate and cooling, a solid (1.6g) separated; this was crystallised from dilute hydrobromic acid, and had m.p. 129°. It afforded a picrate, m.p. 200°(d) (Found: N, 19.31; $C_5H_8N_2S$. $C_6H_5N_3O_7$, requires N 19.60%). It also gave a derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate on boiling for five min. in methanolic solution, m.p. 188° (Found: S, 23.91; $C_{11}H_{13}N_2S_2$, requires S 24.5%).

The product from α -bromoacetone and methyl thiocarbamide described by earlier workers^{4,5,6} as 2-methylamino-4-methyl thiazole, was found identical through mixed m.p. of various common derivatives, with the above product.

*Excepting in the case of acetone and ethyl methyl ketone where the reaction was carried out for 16 hrs. in a large excess of refluxing ketone mixed with a little water.

TABLE I

Interaction of methyl/benzyl formamidine disulphide dihydrobromides with ketones,

Sl. No.	Reactants	Duration of heating (hrs)	Name of the product and formula	yield*	m.p.** (°C.)	Analyses Found (%)	Analyses Reqd. (%)	Derivatives and reactions
1.	Acetone(100 ml) + +MeFDS(3.5 g) + Water(10 ml)	16	2-imino-3,4-dimethyl-4-thiazoline hydrobromide (IA) $C_9H_{10}N_2S \cdot HBr$	1.6 g (76.1%)	129	N 13.07 S 15.04	13.39 15.31 Mol. Eq. 207.9	Hydrochloride, m.p. 225°. Picrate, m.p. 200°(d). Derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate, m.p. 188°.
2	Acetone(30 ml.) + BzFDS(5 g)	12	2-benzylamino-4-methylthiazole hydrobromide (IIB) $C_{11}H_{14}N_2S \cdot HBr$	1.5 g (53.5%)	240	H 4.52 N 9.37 S 10.63	46.63 46.31 4.56 9.82 11.22 Mol. Eq. 284.1	285.0 Picrate, m.p. 155°.
3	Ethyl methyl Ketone(30 ml) + McFDS(3.5 g) + Water(5 ml)	16	2-imino-3, 4, 5-trimethyl-4-thiazoline*** (IIIA) $C_6H_{10}N_2S$	1.8 g (71.4%)	127	N 19.42 S 22.16	19.71 22.53	Hydrobromide, m.p. 268°. Picrate, m.p. 193°. Derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate, m.p. 231° found: reqd. for $C_{13}H_{15}N_2S_2$ S 22.79% 23.10
4	Ethyl methyl ketone(20 ml) + BzFDS(3 g)	6	3-benzyl-4, 5-dimethyl-2-imino-4-thiazoline hydrobromide (IIB) $C_{18}H_{18}N_2S \cdot HBr$	1.9 g (43.3%)	251	H 4.99 N 9.21 S 10.43	48.16 48.16 5.01 9.36 10.70 Mol. Eq. 300.5	299.0 Derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate, m.p. 203° found: reqd. for $C_{19}H_{19}N_2S_2$ S 17.94% 18.19%
5	Acetophenone (2 ml) + McFDS(3.5 g)	2½	2-imino-3-methyl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline hydrobromide (IVA) $C_{16}H_{16}N_2S \cdot HBr$	1.4 g (51.8%)	274(d)	N 10.22 S 11.56	10.33 11.80	Picrate, m.p. 178°. Derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate, m.p. 180° found: reqd. for $C_{17}H_{17}N_2S_2$ S 19.37% 19.69%
6	Acetophenone (2 ml) + BzFDS(3 g)	2½	3-benzyl-2-imino-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline hydrobromide (IVB) $C_{16}H_{14}N_2S \cdot HBr$	1.6 g (45.7%)	243	H 4.06 N 7.85 S 8.94	4.32 8.07 9.22	Sulphate, m.p. 130° (found SO_4^{2-} 15.59%; $(C_{16}H_{14}N_2S)_2 H_2SO_4$ reqs. 15.2%) Nitrate, m.p. 184°(d) Picrate, m.p. 174°. Derivative with phenylisothiocyanate, m.p. 196°.

TABLE I (contd.)

Sl. No.	Reactants	Duration of heating (hrs.)	Name of the product and formula	Yield*	m.p.** (°C.)	Analyses Found (%)	Req. (%)	Derivatives and reactions
7	Ethyl acetoacetate (6 ml) + MeFDS (3.5 g)	4	5-carbethoxy-4-methyl-2-methylamino thiazole (VIA) $C_8H_{12}N_2SO_2$	1.1 g (55.0%)	154	N 13.74 S 15.62	14.00 16.00	Hydrobromide, m.p. 2200° (d) (found N, 9.62%; reqd. for $C_8H_{12}N_2S.HBr$ 9.96%)
8	Ethyl acetoacetate (6 ml) + BzFDS (5 g)	4	2-benzylamino-5-carbethoxy-4-methyl thiazole hydrobromide (VI B) $C_{14}H_{16}N_2SO_2.HBr$	1.0 g (27.7%)	232° (d)	N 7.57 Br 22.85 Mol. Eq. 355.8	7.84 22.40 357.0	Free base, m.p. 112° (found N, 9.71; reqd. for $C_{14}H_{16}N_2SO_2$ 10.14%)
9	Cyclohexanone (6 ml) + MeFDS (3.5 g)	4	(a) Spiro-[(1,2,3,6,7,8-hexahydro-2-methylimino-3,1,4-benzothiazine-4,1'-cyclohexane] (VIIA) $C_{14}H_{21}N_2S$ (b) 2-imino-3-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-benzothiazoline hydrochloride (VIII A) $C_8H_{12}N_2S.HCl$	1.0 g (40.6%) 0.9 g (43.9%)	162 266° (d)	N 11.03 S 12.62 N 13.41 S 15.52 Mol. Eq. 203.1	11.24 12.85 13.69 15.64 204.5	Picrate, m.p. 226°. Picrate, m.p. 195°. Derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate, m.p. 246° (found S, 20.87%; reqd. for $C_{12}H_{17}N_3S_2$ 21.12%)
10	Cyclohexanone (6 ml) + BzFDS (5 g)	4	(a) Spiro-[(2-benzylimino-1,2,3,6,7,8-hexahydro-3,1,4-benzothiazine-4,1'-cyclohexane] hydrobromide (VII B) $C_{20}H_{26}N_2S.HBr$ (b) 3-benzyl-2-imino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-benzothiazoline hydrobromide (VIII B) $C_{14}H_{16}N_2S.HBr$	2.0 g (49.1%) 1.2 g (26.2%)	202 252	C 59.27 H 6.69 N 6.52 S 7.59 Mol. Eq. 406.1 C 50.52 H 5.60 N 8.34 S 9.37 Mol. Eq. 326.8	58.96 6.63 6.85 7.86 407.0 51.69 5.29 8.61 9.84 325.0	Picrate, m.p. 218°. Hydrochloride, m.p. 202°. Free base, m.p. 67°. Hydrochloride, m.p. 278°. Free base, m.p. 87°. Derivative with phenyl isothiocyanate, m.p. 216° (found N, 10.79%; reqd. for $C_{21}H_{27}N_3S_2$ 11.08%)

* All yields were calculated on the amount of disulphide used.

** Solvents for crystallisation were either dilute acids or alcohols.

*** Its hydrochloride is reported to melt at 282-3° (C.A. 48, 2781).

† MeFDS denotes bis-methyl formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide.

‡ BzFDS denotes bis-benzyl formamidine disulphide dihydrobromide.

Synthesis of Compounds I, II, V, VI, VII, VIIIA, and XB. The reactants (for details vide Table 2) were heated for 1 to 2 hr. at 110-120°. At the end of the reaction, the product was washed with acetone, the acetone insoluble solid basified with dilute sodium hydroxide and the free base thus obtained crystallised from ethanol. These experiments are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Synthesis of IA, IIB, V, VI, VII, VIIIA and XB.

Sl. No.	Reactants (g)	Name of the product and formula	m.p. (°C.)	yield*	Analyses found(%) reqd.(%)	Comparison with compn. from Table I
1.	α -bromo acetone (1.4)	methyl thio-carbamide. 2-imino-3,4-dimethyl-4** thiazoline hydrobromide (IA) $C_5H_8N_2S.HBr$	129	0.8 g (40.3%)		Identical with IA.
2.	-do- (1.7)	benzyl thio-carbamide. 2-benzylamino-4-methyl thiazole hydrobromide (IIB) $C_{11}H_{12}N_2S.HBr$	240	0.6 g (21.0%)	Mol. Eq. 283.6 285.6	Identical with IIB.
3.	Ethyl α -chloro acetate (1.7)	methyl thio-carbamide. 5-carbethoxy-4-methyl-2-methylamino thiazole- (VIA) $C_9H_{12}N_2SO_2$	153	0.8 g (40.0%)	N 13.82 14.06	Identical with VIA.
4.	-do- (1.7)	benzyl thio-carbamide. 2-benzylamino-5-carbethoxy-4-methyl thiazole (VIB) $C_{14}H_{16}N_2SO_2$	112	1.4 g (50.0%)	N 9.82 10.01	Identical with VIB.
5.	Phenacyl bromide (2.0 g)	methyl thio-carbamide 2-methylamino-4-phenyl thiazole (VA) $C_{10}H_{10}N_2S$	138	1.5 g (77.7%)	N 14.42 14.73	
6.	-do- (1.7)	benzyl thio-carbamide. 2-benzylamino-4-phenyl thiazole (VB) $C_{16}H_{14}N_2S$	98	2.0 g (74.2%)	N 10.32 10.52 S 11.74 12.03	
7.	Cyclohexyl cyclohexanone hydrochloride (2.3)	methylthio-carbamide Spiro-[(1,2,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-2-methylimino-3,1,4-) benzothiazine-4,1'-cyclohexane] (VIIA) $C_{14}H_{20}N_2S$	163	2.2 g (88.6%)	N 11.10 11.24	Identical with VIIA.
8.	-do- (1.7)	benzyl thio-carbamide. Spiro-[(2-benzylimino-1,2,5,6,7,8-hexahydro-3,1,4-) benzothiazine-4,1'-cyclohexane] (VIIB) $C_{20}H_{26}N_2S$	68	2.4 g (72.2%)	N 8.32 8.58	Identical with VIIB.
9.	2-chloro cyclohexanone (1.4 g)	methyl thio-carbamide. 2-imino-3-methyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-benzothiazoline hydrochloride (VIII) $C_8H_{12}N_2S.HCl$	267(d)	0.6 g (30.0%)	N 13.41 13.69 S 15.32 15.64	Identical with VIII.
10.	-do- (1.7)	benzyl thio-carbamide. 2-benzylamino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro benzothiazole (XB) $C_{14}H_{16}N_2S$	118	1.3 g (58.7%)	N 11.25 11.47 S 12.84 13.11	

* Yields were based on the amount of thiocarbamides used.

** The experimental procedure was as described by Burtles⁵.

Attempted Interconversion of 2-Benzylamino-4-phenylthiazole IVB into 2-Imino-3-benzyl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline Hydrobromide (VB) and vice versa.—The 2-benzylamino-4-phenyl thiazole IVB, m.p. 98°, obtained from phenacyl bromide and benzyl thiocarbamide

mide (*vide* Table 2, Expt No. 6), was refluxed with 48% hydrobromic acid for 1½ hr. but no change was observed. Similarly the 2-imino-3-benzyl-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline hydrobromide (VB) m.p. 243°, was heated with benzyl amine at 110° for 1½ hr. without any change.

The author desires to thank Prof. R. H. Sahasrabudhey for his interest, the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for a Junior Research Fellowship and the authorities of B.H.U. and Nagpur University for laboratory facilities.

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Received April 4, 1966.